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MILESTONE REPORT

TEST RFID TAGGING FOR IRRADIATION FACILITIES

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Abstract:

Task 4.3 with WP4 develop common systems and procedures for European irradiation facilities. The current irradiation facilities at CERN and across EU play a strong role in the R&D for the next generation of particle physics detectors. To cope with the increasing user demand and to optimise the performance of the facilities a series of improvement were studied within the AIDAInnova project. Among them, to support a clear identification of the, often radioactive, samples throughout their life cycle, a new integrated RFID based system is being integrated and evaluated for both the IRRAD facility at CERN and the ITA (Irradiation Test Area) at FNAL. The CAEN DIGIWASTE platform for radioactive waste management is at the basis of this work. The purpose of this MS report is to summarize and describe the irradiation tests performed on different types of RFID tags in order to contribute to the selection of the one operating reliably in the facility environment and compatible with the new CAEN platform and tools being integrated.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2024.

For more information on AIDAinnova, its partners and contributors please see <http://aidainnova.web.cern.ch/>

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Executive summary

This report describes the tests of RFID tags carried out in three radiation test facilities, which could represent the spectrum of potential applications of RFID tags for radiation testing setups traceability. Radiation test on RFID tag samples have been thus performed at the CERN-IRRAD facility with protons (for Total Ionising Dose effect), at the ENEA FNG facility with 14 MeV neutrons (for Single Event Effects and Displacement Damage effects), and finally at CERN-CHARM mixed field facility to simulate and test the long term and reliable operation of the tags.

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the past years, the CERN IRRAD proton irradiation facility team has developed a custom data management system capable of keeping track of several aspects of the irradiation tests performed. This system is named IRRAD Data Manager (IDM) [1]. In the framework of the AIDAinnova H2020 project, the integration of the existing IDM with an RFID tagging system (CAEN DIGIWASTE) is being conducted [2]. This would allow following the samples before and after the irradiation, tracking their position wirelessly inside the facility.

IDM is also foreseen to be extended to different irradiation facilities, with different radiation fields including protons, neutrons, photons, also in mix-field configuration such as the CERN Gamma Irradiation Facility (GIF++) or the FNAL Irradiation Test Area (ITA) [2]. For this reason, evaluating the radiation hardness of RFID tags under different radiation fields, with doses and fluences of the order of the ones foreseen in Radiation Hardness testing, is mandatory. RFID tags could in fact integrate doses and fluences close to the ones targeted for the Devices Under Test (DUT), being the tags ideally attached to the DUT boards.

This report describes the tests of RFID tags carried out in three radiation test facilities, which could represent the spectrum of potential applications of RFID tags for radiation testing setups traceability. Radiation test on RFID tag samples have been thus performed at the CERN-IRRAD [3] facility with protons (for Total Ionising Dose effect), at the ENEA FNG [4] facility with 14 MeV neutrons (for Single Event Effects and Displacement Damage effects), and finally at CERN-CHARM [3] mixed field facility to simulate and test the long term and reliable operation of the tags.

2. 23-GEV PROTON IRRADIATION (IRRAD)

A first test campaign with protons of 24 GeV has been performed at the IRRAD facility at CERN. The aim was to irradiate the tags with protons to reach total ionising doses of hundreds of Gy.

A total of six irradiations have been performed at IRRAD. After the first two irradiations up to ~100 Gy, no damage was observed in the tags. The target fluences were selected to match a previous study where tags were irradiated with gamma-rays in three steps 1, 10 and 100 Gy. The gamma study concluded that tags weren't affected up to 100 Gy and thus proton and gamma irradiations results appear to be consistent. Coincidentally, only one additional irradiation up to 200 Gy was needed to observe tags failures.

A full report about this campaign has been prepared and uploaded to Zenodo public repository. The document is available here <https://zenodo.org/record/5846412>.

3. 14-MEV NEUTRON IRRADIATION (FNG)

A second test campaign with 14 MeV neutrons has been performed at the FNG facility belonging to the ENEA Frascati research centre. The aim was to irradiate the tags with fast neutrons to verify the Single Event Effects and Displacement Damage effects on the tags.

A total of nine tags were tested at FNG, one was located on the stairs far away from the neutron source and used as a reference (also to be constantly read by the antenna). The other eight tags were placed in front of the source. For the first step, the location was uniform as the tags were at 16 cm from the source, but the integrated number of neutrons about one order of magnitude less than the following steps ($\sim 1E11$ n/cm²). This allowed for a slow ramp-up of the instantaneous flux and to check the tag behaviour with operational fluxes. During the following steps tags were irradiated to higher fluences thanks to a different location of the tags, now placed between 4 cm and 6 cm. Different distances meant different fluences reaching a maximum of about $7E12$ n/cm². After several irradiation steps, all the RFID tags were still fully functional. The EPC and the volatile memory being readable and writable, with no bit flip detected, and with only a slight reduction of the RSSI response signal strength from the interrogated tag. The final neutron fluence level (corresponding to a TID of roughly 70-80 Gy) is a typical target fluence for high flux radiation hardness test with 14 MeV neutrons, and more generally with fast neutrons in the MeV range. These results, consistent with the previous irradiation experiments, show the possibility to use these tags for fast neutron facilities, where the target fluence will be below $1E13$ n/cm².

A full report about this campaign has been prepared and uploaded to Zenodo public repository. The document is available here <https://zenodo.org/records/7846196>.

4. MIXED-FIELD NEUTRON IRRADIATION (CHARM)

A last test on selected RFID tags was performed at the CHARM mixed field facility at CERN. This test aims at verifying the results achieved in single radiation fields, with a mix-particle environment where the single field components will reach comparable total values. Moreover, this test campaign also aims to simulate and test the long term and reliable operation of the tags.

4.1. CHARM RADIATION FIELD

The CHARM mixed field is generated by 24 GeV/c protons from the PS ring, impacting a copper target of 5 cm diameter and 50 cm length, parallel to the beam direction.

Secondary field includes protons, pions, electrons and positrons, photons, and neutrons. Depending on the position around the target, the mixed field components relative abundance changes. For these tests, two positions (lateral w.r.t. the target) were used: the “overhead conveyor” and the “G0” position. Both chosen positions exploit the same type of particle field (with similar composition, e.g. particle spectra) but deliver two different radiation (e.g. fluence) levels, being located at two different distances from the target. The particle energy spectra expected in these two lateral positions, as well as the G0 location facing the CHARM target area, are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: CHARM mixed field spectrum in lateral positions with respect to the target (left-hand side). The “GO” position during the RFID tag samples installation (right-hand side).

4.2. TESTED SAMPLES AT CHARM

The RFID tags were assessed in CHARM following the test procedure detailed in the documents indicated in section 2 of this report. The details about the type of RFID are also available on the same references. The samples for the CHARM irradiation were labelled using the subsequent identification patterns: SET-005250 and SET-005245 that were placed in the overhead conveyor and SET-005244, SET-005243, SET-005248, SET-005249, SET-005246 that were placed in the CHARM position labelled G0.

After configuring the RFID reader (HEX Multipurpose RAIN RFID Reader, <https://www.caenrfid.com/en/products/hex-r1290i/>) adequately, the measurements consisted in measuring the Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) as well as the memory integrity (reading and writing capabilities). The RSSI is used to evaluate the detection range of the tag. As the system records the RSSI with a negative value, one can consider getting the absolute value for the analysis. As an absolute value, the higher the number, the weaker the signal.

The following procedure was repeated before and after irradiating the samples and can be described as the following:

1. Place the tag directly on the reader (lowest distance).
2. Test the tag before irradiation.
 - a. Test if reader can detect tag by launching an inventory.
 - b. Test if the user memory contains the same values as before the test.
 - c. Report the maximum absolute RSSI value.
 - d. Test if RFID reader can overwrite consistently the first 8 bytes of the user memory section (labelled USER in the application).
 - e. Restore original memory values for first 8 bytes of user memory section.
 - f. Return to sub-step 2.a and place the RFID at 29 mm between from the reader.
3. Irradiate tag up to target fluence.
4. Restart from step 2 after irradiation.

The below table summarised the outcomes of the pre-irradiation samples characterization based on RFIDs tests.

Overhead conveyor:

Sample	RFID	Timestamp	READER OK	RSSI on the READER	RSSI at 2.9 cm from the READER	Altered Bits	Reading OK for both distances	Writing OK for both distances
SET-005245	300833B2DDD9014000000000	20/08/2024 11:15:23	TRUE	-465	-500	0	TRUE	TRUE
SET-005250	E280689400005001F4B4C96C	20/08/2024 11:02:44	TRUE	-475	-495	0	TRUE	TRUE

G0:

Sample	RFID	Timestamp	READER OK	RSSI on the READER	RSSI at 2.9 cm from the READER	Altered Bits	Reading OK for both distances	Writing OK for both distances
SET-005243	300833B2DDD90140000000002	20/08/2024 11:25:17	TRUE	-465	-485	0	TRUE	TRUE
SET-005244	300833B2DDD90140000000001	20/08/2024 11:18:07	TRUE	-445	-475	0	TRUE	TRUE
SET-005246	E2806F12000000021F918042	20/08/2024 11:10:44	TRUE	-505	-545	0	TRUE	TRUE
SET-005248	E280689400004001F4B50431	20/08/2024 11:06:59	TRUE	-505	-525	0	TRUE	TRUE
SET-005249	E280689400004001F4B50432	20/08/2024 11:04:52	TRUE	-525	-545	0	TRUE	TRUE

The below table summarised the outcomes of the post-irradiation samples characterization based on RFIDs tests. These data refer to the measurement run performed after the second irradiation step detailed in Section 4.3

Overhead conveyor:

Sample	RFID	Timestamp	READER OK	RSSI on the READER	RSSI at 2.9 cm from the READER	Altered Bits	Reading OK for both distances	Writing OK for both distances
SET-005245	300833B2DDD90140000000000	26/09/2024 17:05:20	TRUE	-425	-465	0	TRUE	TRUE
SET-005250	E280689400005001F4B4C96C	26/09/2024 16:53:25	TRUE	-425	-525	2	TRUE	TRUE

G0:

Sample	RFID	Timestamp	READER OK	RSSI on the READER	RSSI at 2.9 cm from the READER	Altered Bits	Reading OK for both distances	Writing OK for both distances
SET-005243	300833B2DDD90140000000002	26/09/2024 16:37:41	TRUE	-425	-425	0	TRUE	TRUE
SET-005244	300833B2DDD90140000000001	26/09/2024 17:02:03	TRUE	-425	-425	0	TRUE	TRUE
SET-005246	E2806F12000000021F918042	26/09/2024 16:57:22	TRUE	-525	-565	0	TRUE	TRUE
SET-005248	E280689400004001F4B50431	26/09/2024 16:43:50	TRUE	-425	-525	0	TRUE	TRUE
SET-005249	E280689400004001F4B50432	26/09/2024 16:48:27	TRUE	-425	-525	0	TRUE	TRUE

4.3. RADIATION LEVELS AND RESULTS

The cumulated radiation levels, in the two different positions, by the different tag sets, are shown in the tables below. Here Total Ionising Dose (TID), High Energy Hadrons (HEH), that is hadrons with energy greater than 20 MeV, 1 MeV equivalent neutron fluence (1MeVeqN/cm²), and Thermal neutron fluence (ThN) are listed. Moreover, the last column, summarizes the status of the tags after the irradiation step.

Overhead conveyor

TID (Gy)	HEH/cm ²	1MeVeqN/cm ²	ThN/cm ²	Tag status
154	6.7E11	1.8E12	5.2E11	All OK
348	1.5E12	4.4E12	1.2E12	Not all ok

G0

TID (Gy)	HEH/cm ²	1MeVeqN/cm ²	ThN/cm ²	Tag status
40	1.3E11	5.5E11	2.5E11	All OK
84	2.7E11	1.4E12	4.3E11	All OK

After the highest dose, when the sample SET-005250 was read, the memory integrity was found to be compromised (2 bytes of the USER memory were modified – the 2nd and 3rd to the last). This result in CHARM is consistent with the one obtained earlier at IRRAD and FNG, confirming that the threshold for the appearance of radiation effects in high-energy particle radiation fields is located at a Total Dose exceeding some hundred Gy.

5. CONCLUSION

The measurements performed at CHARM and FNG reached typical fluence levels for radiation hardness tests qualification of electronics components and/or systems in particle accelerators environment or other application such as space or avionics. In CHARM the first failure appeared after two weeks of irradiation in mixed field which corresponds to a standard irradiation slot assigned to radiation effects users. It has also to be noted that the observed failure was minor and did not compromise the operation of the tag itself, but only its user memory. Different is the case of the IRRAD test where the tags were exposed directly to the proton beam to rapidly test the upper limit of the tolerable damage. In a real application within a beam facility as IRRAD at CERN, the tags won't be exposed directly to the particle beam but rather sit next to the sample being irradiated (e.g. a few cm from it) thus experiencing a background radiation field which is comparable to the one used in the CHARM or FNG radiation tests presented here.

As a conclusion, the experimental results compiled in this MS15 report show the possibility to reasonably use these tags in the radiation test facility environments by coupling them with the associated CAEN platform and tools as also shown in the previous MS14 report [2].

6. REFERENCES

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